

From Passive Learners to Active Participants: Empowering Engineering Students through Experiential Learning

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Abstract

Engineering students play a crucial role as agents of innovation and technological advancement, influencing technology's development and its impact on society. To effectively prepare them for this pivotal role, it is imperative to cultivate a strong sense of responsibility and autonomy in their professional development. However, achieving this in traditional classroom settings can be challenging and may stifle their ability to engage with societal issues actively. Passive learning environments risk relegating students to passive participants in social progress. Traditional problem-solving methods must be improved in the face of global challenges such as pandemics, conflicts, and environmental crises. Recognizing this, the Seminars course in the Master of Industrial Engineering and Management (MIEM), second year, first semester, introduced a novel challenge: in teams, to organize an event (e.g., roundtable, training, company visit, among others) exploring an IEM topic. This paper describes the implementation of this challenge. Teams were tasked with planning and running events within the scheduled lecture times. Eight teams, each consisting of five to seven members, enthusiastically accepted the challenge and covered various topics in their events. Event evaluation was multi-criteria, with teams judging each other's events against pre-defined metrics. Overall, student performance was commendable, and participants expressed satisfaction and pride in their achievements. Feedback gathered through end-of-term questionnaires (with a 68% response rate) revealed a high level of appreciation for the autonomy and creativity that the challenge provided. However, there is a notable concern regarding attendance at peer-organized events, with over 50% of students attending all events. This discrepancy between students' desire for meaningful education and their participation in co-curricular activities suggests a missed opportunity for impactful learning experiences. Addressing this gap could increase student engagement and foster a deeper understanding of societal issues within the educational context.

Keywords: Active Learning; Experiential Learning; Transformative Learning; Industrial Engineering and Management Education.

1 Introduction

The ongoing discussion on integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is crucial (Majeed & Hwang, 2024; Rahayu, 2023). However, equality is vital for Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), particularly Engineering Schools, to prepare the future engineering workforce for an unpredictable work environment, with or without AI assistance. In this context, the role of active learning methodologies becomes even more significant. It is widely accepted that while teachers can impart knowledge, students genuinely learn when actively engaging in the learning process. This means that students must be involved in their learning. Otherwise, learning will not occur, placing additional demands on teachers, who must strive to be innovators.

In addition, students' behaviour must change from passive learners to active participants. By doing this, they can pull what they want to learn, and they will be developing skills recognized by world organizations (World Economic Forum, 2015, 2018, 2022; World Manufacturing Forum, 2019) as fundamental to help students use technologies properly. These are: 1) creative problem-solving; 2) entrepreneurial mindset; 3) intercultural and disciplinary inclusive and diversity-oriented mindset, 4) ability to handle increasing complexity, 5) effective communication skills, and 6) open-mindedness towards constant change.

Similar skills (e.g., critical thinking, problem-solving, teamwork, communication and negotiation skills, analytical skills, creativity, and intercultural skills) are embedded in the key competences defined by the Council of the

European Union (Council of the European Union, 2018). According to this Council, the eight key competencies for lifelong learning are: 1) Literacy; 2) Multilingual; 3) Mathematical, science, technology, and engineering; 4) Digital; 5) Personal, Social, and Learning to Learn; 6) Citizenship; 7) Entrepreneurship and; 8) Cultural awareness and expression (Council of the European Union, 2018, p. 15). The fifth (Personal, Social, and Learning to Learn) key competence was the base for a European Framework called LifeComp (Sala et al., 2020). All competencies and skills are equally important; each contributes to a successful societal life.

To achieve this, students need an educational environment suitable for this development. An environment that promotes the freedom for the learner to become a connector, creator, and constructivist, as advocated by Education 3.0 (Gerstein, 2013). Students also need to be innovators and agents of their learning as education evolves through Education 4.0 (Chea & Huan, 2019; Costan et al., 2021; González-Pérez & Ramírez-Montoya, 2022; Gowripeddi et al., 2021; Miranda et al., 2021) and Education 5.0 (Alharbi, 2023; Dervojeda, 2021). Active learning methodologies, which put students at the centre of the learning process, provide the environment for this development. These methodologies have been proven to be highly effective in fostering student engagement and learning outcomes (Alves et al., 2018, 2022; Bonwell & Eison, 1991; Dewey, 1916; Felder & Brent, 2006; Felder et al., 2000; Kang, 2019; Prince, 2004).

This paper is grounded in the context of the Seminars in Industrial Engineering and Management (SIEM), the academic year of 2023_24. In this setting, the authors of this paper embarked on a paradigm shift. Instead of the traditional approach where teachers prepare the seminar class for the students, the students take the lead in preparing the seminar class for the teachers. The idea was to empower the students to pull the topics that interested them the most. This approach facilitated the development of the competencies and skills mentioned earlier. The paper's objective is to detail this experiential learning, its setup, and the students' feedback on it.

This paper is organized into six sections. The first section introduces the context and objectives of the paper. Section 2 provides a brief background on transformative learning. Section 3 presents the materials and methods used to assess the students and collect feedback. The fourth section offers an overview of the IEM Master program, with a detailed description of the Seminars in the IEM course. Section 5 presents the students' results and feedback regarding this activity. Finally, the last section draws conclusions based on the findings.

2 Background

Engineering Education is always a topic of interest. Despite all the changes that new technologies (e.g., AI, Virtual/Augmented reality) or new learning methodologies bring to it, there are fundamental principles that always remain the same as they are crucial to address the specific needs of engineers' future professionals. According to King (2012), these are: 1) more understanding of the human condition, cultures, and society; 2) an ability to work effectively with public policy, business, and government; 3) an understanding of the process of innovation and factors contributing toward it; 4) an ability to work in synergy with persons from other disciplines, including both other science and engineering fields and non-science/engineering fields, such as business, law, economics, public policy, political science, and sociology; 5) an ability to communicate and to express technical issues in simple, understandable terms; and 6) general liberal education integrated with engineering education.

From the earliest reports and surveys (ASCE, 2009; ASME Board of Education, 2012; Duderstadt, 2008; National Academy of Engineering, 2012; UNESCO, 2005, 2010, 2014; World Economic Forum, 2015) to the most recent ones (UNESCO, 2021; World Economic Forum, 2022; World Manufacturing Forum, 2019; World Manufacturing Foundation, 2022) all are aligned in the key competences needed for engineering workforce of future. At the same time, these reports appeal to more effective learning methodologies based on active, hands-on,

experiential learning, among others. These have been used by many teachers (Alves et al., 2017; Alves, 2018; Alves et al., 2022; Alves & Soares, 2020; Bonwell & Eison, 1991; R. Felder & Brent, 2001; Gibbs & Habeshaw, 1992; Lima et al., 2007, 2017; Oliveira et al., 2020; Soares & Alves, 2021a).

Using such methodologies, students will benefit and truly transform through a meaningful learning experience and a transformative learning environment, allowing them to develop autonomous thinking (Cate & Heer, 2018; Mezirow, 1997). In this environment, teachers become facilitators and provocateurs rather than authorities (Zhang et al., 2008). The teacher's role is to help students encouragement to create norms for better organization, order, justice, and civility in the classroom, to respect and be responsible for helping each other to learn, to welcome diversity, to foster peer collaboration and equal opportunity for participation (Danila, 2018; Mezirow, 1997). Also, teachers should engage students, assigning them the responsibility to assume a more active role in their learning with their peers and in collaboration networks (Alharbi, 2023; Derojeda, 2021; Zhang et al., 2008). Transformative learning is the essence of adult education (Knowles, 1980; Mezirow, 1997; Misawa & McClain, 2019).

3 Materials and methods

The research strategy employed was a case study focusing on cohort 2023_24 of 52 students in the first semester of the second year of the IEM Master program. This cohort was chosen for its relevance to the study's objectives, which aimed to assess the outcomes of the Seminar of Industrial Engineering and Management (SIEM) course activities. Furthermore, when the semester concluded, a designed online questionnaire evaluated the key competencies developed through this activity. This instrument, presented in Appendix A, was used to gather student feedback and record their observations. Titled: "Autonomy and motivation in the organization of an event at the Industrial Engineering and Management Seminar", the questionnaire comprised 35 items: 31 closed items and four open-ended items. The closed items were scored on a Likert scale [1: Totally disagree to 5: Totally agree], and one was a checkbox question (Q15).

The questionnaire was divided into six sections, each containing a variable number of items (Appendix A). This questionnaire was adapted from a previous one used for other pedagogical activities (Alves & Soares, 2020; Soares & Alves, 2021a, 2021b). The sections' categories were inspired by the skills embedded in the eight key competences proposed by the Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (Council of the European Union, 2018), as referred to in section I. For example, question 1 of section II of the questionnaire was related to the student's attitude when they read the task statement, i.e., if they got curious about that and looked for material for its execution. This attitude reveals pro-activity and problem-solving skills embedded in literacy and entrepreneurship competencies.

Thirty-two filled questionnaires were collected, representing a response rate of 62%. In this specific study case, a response rate of 62% is considered suitable for statistical analysis, as it closely corresponds to the proportion of students actively engaging in peer activities throughout the class duration, thereby supporting the validity of our research.

Besides the descriptive analysis of the collected data, hierarchical clustering was selected for the statistical analysis due to its ability to identify natural groupings within a dataset based on similarity measures, uncover underlying patterns and structures within the data, and allow the exploration of the relationships between different questionnaire items. Also, a thematic analysis of the students' answers to the open-ended questions of the questionnaire was performed to gain insights into students' perceptions and experiences related to the seminars' activities development.

4 Study context

This section presents the context of the Industrial Engineering and Management Master (IEM) considered in this paper. Two years ago, this master's degree underwent a curricular restructuring and is now divided into a three-year Bachelor's program (first-cycle) and a two-year master's program (second-cycle). It is part of the curriculum offered by the Department of Production and Systems of the School of Engineering of the University of Minho. This second-cycle master's program comprises 120 European Credit Transfer Systems (ECTS). The first semester of the second year comprises six courses, each worth five ECTS, with Seminars in Industrial Engineering and Management (SEIM) being one of them. The second year includes a Master's dissertation worth 30 ECTS, typically developed within an industrial context. The Seminars in Industrial Engineering and Management course, along with its structure and setup, is described in the following sections.

4.1 Seminars in Industrial Engineering and Management

The objectives of the SIEM course were described in the educational offer of the University of Minho website (UMinho, 2024) as *"Seminars focused on advanced engineering subjects with the participation of invited speakers. This course aims to provide students with the acquisition of knowledge and skills within the different seminars that will be organized on the topics addressed. The topics covered will focus on advanced engineering topics."*. It is expected to be 95 hours of autonomous work and 45 hours of classes in a semester that starts in September and finishes in January.

4.2 Organization and setting up the activity

After the activity and its purpose were introduced to the students in the first class, students organized themselves into teams: five teams of seven members, two teams with six members, and one with five members, for a total of 52 students. Teams were invited to add their team constitutions to a Padlet created for this course, which is in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Padlet extract with teams formed for the course SEIM (in Portuguese)

The responsible for the SEIM course created a written document with the assignment instructions and assessment methods and shared an Excel in Google Drive for the teams to add the theme and date (week) preferred. The activities organized by the teams started in the fourth week to give them time to prepare the activity. In each session, each team approached a different topic related to Industrial Engineering and Management using a different mode to introduce the activity and identify the invited speaker(s), as described in Table 1 in more detail.

Table 1. Topics approached by the teams in each session.

Date	Team nr.	Description	Speakers
2023/10/02	Team 6	Roundtable related with the master dissertation, in Portuguese the team called "A dissertação chegou. E agora?"	IEM Alumni
2023/10/23	Team 5	Talk related with EIM and the future challenges: "O papel da Engenharia Industrial & Os desafios para o futuro."	IEM Alumni
2023/10/30	Team 8	Roundtable related with leadership and team management: "Liderança e Gestão de Equipa".	IEM Alumni and others speakers
2023/11/06	Team 7	Talk and Workshop about the importance of an efficient logistic: "Importância de uma logística eficiente na gestão das organizações". Then the team organized a game to play in practice layout and logistic concepts.	IEM Alumni and other speaker
2023/11/13	Team 4	Training session about SAP system	PwC coworkers
2023/11/16	Team 3	Company visit	Company coworkers
2023/11/27	Team 2	Escape EGI Game and a Talk	CEO of a company
2023/12/04	Team 1	Stadium visit (Vitória Sport Clube), talk, case study resolution about role of IEM in sport: "O papel de EGI no desporto" and discussion about the people flow in games days and impact in safety. Then, the team invited two singers to animate the visit.	Safety Director

This activity assessment involved different criteria with different weights, represented in

Table 2.

Table 2. Assessment criteria and weight of each.

Criteria	Weight (%)
Preparation of the activity	20
Relevance for the Industrial Engineering and Management area and creativity	25
Presentation and exposition by the speaker	15
Assessment by the other teams	10
Activity record in Padlet and report describing the activity, objectives, motivation, theme interest	25
Delivery of all materials used (e.g., flyer)	5

Teams had to assess colleagues' activities using a similar criteria teachers used. For this, teachers provided them with a questionnaire using Google Forms with four main questions about the preparation of the activity (30%), relevance for the Industrial Engineering and Management area (30%), presentation and exposition of the activity by the speaker (30%), and originality and creativity (10%).

5 Teams achievements and feedback

This section presents the teams' achievements and discusses the questionnaire results, which fulfil the paper's main objective of understanding whether and how students perceived the development of their competences and skills towards empowerment.

5.1 Achievements

All teams successfully tackled the challenge with great enthusiasm. They demonstrated high levels of engagement by inviting speakers from diverse backgrounds, each addressing topics of personal interest. The extent of their involvement was evident in the multitude of elements they planned and employed to execute the activity, including attendance lists, promotional flyers, certificates, registration forms, and more. Furthermore, they planned coffee breaks and prepared tokens of appreciation for the speakers. An integral component of their promotional efforts was the creation and distribution of flyers, exemplified in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flyers used by the eight teams (in Portuguese)

The data collected is in Table 3 and includes the number of participants, the number of answers received in the activity assessment questionnaire from the other teams, and the response rate. The response rate is obtained by dividing the number of answers by the number of participants, expressed as a percentage. Additionally, the teams utilized different elements to support the activity, such as flyers, registration forms, and certificates. The total number of different elements available for their use was 28. This value represents the various elements each team develops according to their respective activities.

Table 3. Participants, respondents, response rate and number of elements used by the teams (T1-T8).

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	Average
Number of participants	15	32	23	41		32	33	19	28
Number of answers	27	29	23	28	29	29	26	24	27
Response rate (%)	180	91	100	68		91	79	126	
Number of elements used by each team	14	12	11	14	5	8	14	8	13

Note: Blank cells indicate that the data was not collected or could not be obtained.

Moreover, the students' teams performed well, demonstrating high levels of engagement in captivating their colleagues' interest and attention. Grades awarded to the teams ranged from 85% to 97%, based on the criteria outlined in Table 2 above. These scores slightly surpassed the evaluations they provided to other teams, which fell between 81% to 93%.

5.2 Analysis of questionnaire responses

Due to space limitations, this paper will primarily analyze aggregated data from the questionnaire responses, focusing on key themes aligned with the study's objectives. While the dataset includes responses to all 35 questions, individual analyses will be conducted selectively, with a preference for aggregate data representation, allowing a more comprehensive data exploration. Descriptive statistics, like the median, mean, and coefficient of variance (CV), summarize each question's responses (Table 4). With the focus on the mean, it is possible to identify questions where most students agreed or disagreed and, based on the CV value, the more consistent and varied answers. Table 4 presents the different descriptive statistics values in descending order of the mean value and the summary of the data distribution obtained in Q17 (the highest mean student's agreement) and Q28 (the lowest mean agreement).

Table 4. Descriptive statistics obtained for each question in descending order of the mean value.

Items or questions / Section / Cluster	Statistics Metrics					Distribution
	Mean	CV*	Median	Min	Max	
Q17 / S III / C1	4.59	0.15	5	2	5	
Q18 / S III / C1	4.50	0.20	5	1	5	
Q7 / S II / C1	4.34	0.16	4	3	5	
Q6 / S II / C1	4.31	0.18	4.5	3	5	
Q10 / S III / C1	4.31	0.12	4	3	5	
Q8 / SII / C1	4.28	0.17	4	3	5	
Q2 / S II / C1	4.25	0.18	4	3	5	
Q11 / S III / C1	4.25	0.20	4	2	5	
Q3 / S II / C1	4.19	0.23	4	1	5	
Q20 / S IV / C1	4.19	0.24	5	2	5	
Q30 / S IV / C3	4.19	0.19	4	2	5	
Q12 / S III / C1	4.09	0.25	4	2	5	
Q26 / SIV / C1	4.06	0.24	4	1	5	
Q16 / SIII / C3	4.03	0.20	4	2	5	
Q21 / SIV / C1	4.00	0.27	4	1	5	
Q24 / S IV / C3	4.00	0.21	4	2	5	
Q5 / S II / C1	3.97	0.20	4	2	5	
Q25 / S IV / C1	3.88	0.26	4	1	5	
Q4 / S II / C1	3.75	0.29	4	1	5	
Q1 / S II / C1	3.72	0.24	4	1	5	
Q13 / S III / C1	3.66	0.29	4	1	5	
Q9 / SII / C3	3.59	0.26	4	2	5	
Q22 / SIV / C3	2.87	0.41	3	1	5	
Q29 / SIV / C2	2.81	0.47	3	1	5	
Q27 / S V / C2	2.56	0.45	2	1	5	
Q19 / S IV / C1	2.53	0.41	3	1	5	
Q14 / S III / C3	2.34	0.47	2	1	5	
Q23 / S IV / C2	1.71	0.61	1	1	5	
Q28 / S V / C2	1.53	0.63	1	1	5	

* coefficient of variation (CV) defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean

The contrasting results between the item "Q17. I was able to understand with this activity that the organization of events is also a project" and "Q28. I preferred that others do the task for me" highlight interesting insights into student perceptions and attitudes towards collaborative work and project management.

The high mean score for the item regarding understanding the activity as a project suggests that students recognize event management's organizational and planning aspects. This indicates a positive outcome regarding students' awareness of project management principles and their ability to apply them in practical scenarios. It suggests that students may have gained valuable insights into project management methodologies and the complexities of organizing events. On the other hand, the low evaluation score for the item indicating a preference for others to do the task suggests a potential reluctance towards taking individual responsibility or actively participating in tasks. This may reflect a lack of engagement or motivation among some students, which could impact collaborative efforts and the overall effectiveness of group work.

Based on a hierarchical clustering for Likert scale data, the Ward linkage method is often a suitable choice due to its ability to identify clusters that minimize within-cluster variance, which aligns well with the typical characteristics of Likert scale responses (Budayan et al., 2009) Three main clusters were identified through hierarchical clustering provide valuable insights into the underlying dimensions of the constructs being

measured, enabling a deeper understanding of the factors influencing student perceptions, motivations, and behaviors in the context of the activity (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Three clusters identification obtained using a hierarchical clustering algorithm (the horizontal axis identify the distance at which clustering occurs).

Identifying these three clusters offers a nuanced understanding of student engagement and performance within the seminar context. The first cluster (C1) includes items related to students' self-efficacy beliefs, their level of engagement in learning activities, and their abilities in completing tasks.

Cluster C2 focuses on individual contributions within team settings and the dynamics that unfold during collaborative work. Examining responses in this cluster, which comprises items with the lowest average based on students' answers, it is essential to delve into the underlying factors contributing to these lower ratings, namely collaboratively developing strategies to enhance teamwork effectiveness and ensuring equitable participation among team members.

Cluster C3 encompasses answers related to motivation, engagement, and performance in completing tasks. This cluster sheds light on the factors that drive students' enthusiasm and commitment to the assigned tasks and their effectiveness in task completion. Communication and negotiation skills were identified as playing an important role in the development of the activities. A consensus appears between the lower mean obtained in the items from C2, which focuses on team dynamics and the concepts of communication and negotiation skills. However, the items from C2 present a higher variability, indicating a mixed perception or experiences among students regarding some aspects of teamwork. Individual preferences, communication styles, past experiences, and team composition may contribute to this variability.

Regarding the qualitative data from the open-ended questions, a qualitative analysis was performed based on word clouds generated, offering a nuanced exploration of the underlying themes and sentiments expressed by participants (Figure 6). The main words used by the students to describe what pleased them most (Figure 6a) were "diversity", "activity", "creative", "theme", and "content". "Diversity" related to the variety of topics and "content" covered, while "activity" was associated with the preparation required to complete the task successfully. Similarly, "creativity" encompassed various aspects, such as the inventive nature of activities, collaboration with colleagues, and ideas explored. Additionally, "theme" was linked to the freedom and flexibility to choose topics of interest. In summary, these words collectively express the students' appreciation for the multifaceted nature of the tasks, engaging activities, opportunities for creative expression, and autonomy in selecting themes.

Figure 6. Word cloud generated from the open-ended questions: (a) Q31. What pleased most in this task was..., and (b) considering all four questions of section VI.

Upon analysing the responses to all four open-ended questions from the final section of the questionnaire (Q28 to Q31), it is evident that the most frequently utilized words are consistent across responses (Figure 6b). However, the term “attendance” emerges in connection with various aspects, including class schedules, duration of activities, and sentiments of demotivation and absence, indicating a lack of balance in the participation of some students during the whole semester.

6 Conclusions

This paper explores the answers of engineering students to a unique challenge presented in the Seminars course of the Master of Industrial Engineering and Management (MIEM) program. The challenge involved organizing events and exploring various industrial engineering and management (IEM) topics in teams as an innovative approach to fostering students’ sense of responsibility, autonomy, and engagement in their professional development. Eight teams enthusiastically embraced the challenge of planning and executing diverse events (seminars, training sessions, and visits, among other activities) within the scheduled lecture times. Event evaluations were conducted using predefined metrics, reflecting the multi-criteria nature of the assessment process. Overall, student performance was commendable, with participants expressing satisfaction and pride in their accomplishments.

The findings from this study underscore the effectiveness of experiential learning approaches in cultivating essential competencies among engineering students. The high level of appreciation for the autonomy and creativity afforded by the challenge highlights the value of hands-on, project-based learning experiences in higher education. However, the notable concern regarding attendance at peer-organized events raises important considerations for enhancing student engagement and participation in co-curricular activities. Addressing this gap presents an opportunity to create more impactful learning experiences that foster a deeper understanding of societal issues and promote active engagement in addressing them. By leveraging innovative pedagogical approaches and incorporating meaningful co-curricular activities, educational institutions can better prepare engineering students to tackle real-world challenges and drive positive societal change.

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Appendix A: Questionnaire

Sections of the questionnaire and questions of each section based on Alves et al. (2022).

Section	Items/questions
I. Introduction	---
II. Autonomy and proactivity (9)	Q1. After reading the task/work statement, get curiosity and get immediate material for execution. Q2. I did extra work for this task. Q3. The task offered me an initiative to learn new concepts. Q4. I tried to use the materials that I find. Q5. I retrieved additional information about the topics that interest me. Q6. I didn't wait that the teacher and/or colleagues tell me what to do. Q7. I took responsibility for my learning. Q8. Although working as a team, the activity gave me the various stages of its autonomy. Q9. I had other priorities besides the task.

<p>III. Critical thinking (9)</p>	<p>Q10. I trusted in my abilities to learn different concepts. Q11. I trusted in my ability to prioritize and show the important over the accessory. Q12. The task/work allows me to understand and apply the content in new situations. Q13. The task allowed me to analyse, summarize and evaluate the contents. Q14. I needed more explanation from the teacher to perform this task. Q15. The criteria that I considered for assessing a task are... Q16. The grade obtained to the activity reflected the work performed. Q17. I was able to understand with this activity that the organization of events is also a project. Q18. The organization of events brings challenges that an Industrial Engineering professional must be prepared to deal with.</p>
<p>IV. Motivation and creativity (8)</p>	<p>Q19. The task motivated me to search for scientific articles on the subject. Q20. I was pleased and proud in developing this task/job. Q21. I felt that I learned more from the way this task/work was done. Q22. The main reason for completing the task was to accomplish the course requirements. Q23. I did the task/work to avoid the blame of not doing. Q24. To have a problem to solve motivated me. Q25. I enjoyed spending time learning the contents of the task. Q26. The task/job stimulated my creativity.</p>
<p>V. Teamwork, communication and negotiation (5)</p>	<p>Q27. I completed most of my colleagues' tasks. Q28. I preferred that others do the task for me. Q29. There should be a peer review to distinguish the grade of this task/work from team members because not all members work with the same commitment. Q30. The preparation of this activity required communication and negotiation skills. Q30a. If your answer is positive, give examples.</p>
<p>VI. Open-ended questions (4)</p>	<p>Q31. What pleased most in this task was... Q32. What pleased less in this task was... Q33. what could be improved... Q34. To increase the intervention of the students of other teams during the activity is important to...</p>